

DOI

WPLYW ŚRODOWISKA EDUKACYJNEGO NA ROZWÓJ UCZNIA SZKOŁY PODSTAWOWEJ W WARUNKACH NOWEJ SZKOŁY UKRAIŃSKIEJ

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Adnotacja. Ministerstwo Edukacji i Nauki Ukrainy wdrażając reformę szkół średnich przewiduje utworzenie szkoły, w której dzieci będą uczyć się poprzez działania, natomiast nacisk zostanie położony na rozwój kompetencji, a nie na zapamiętywanie faktów. Artykuł ujawnia główny cel innowacji - stworzenie Nowej szkoły ukraińskiej, centrum wiedzy i możliwości samorealizacji i wszechstronnego rozwoju osobistego każdego dziecka. Ustalono, że szkoła podstawowa jest podstawą (bazą) dla dalszego rozwoju dziecka (wszechstronny rozwój dziecka zgodnie z wiekiem i indywidualnymi cechami i potrzebami psychofizjologicznymi), jej postrzeganie i stosunek do uczenia się. Uzasadnione, że reforma nowoczesnej branży edukacyjnej przewidują troskę o środowisko edukacyjnym. Okazuje się, że głównie nie jest tutaj technika czy meble, ale zmiana środowiska edukacyjnego, która polega na zmianie nastawienia do dziecka: szacunku, uwagi i chęci znalezienia najlepszego sposobu na jego skuteczne uczenie się.

Słowa kluczowe: środowisko, środowisko edukacyjne, nowa szkoła ukraińska, harmonijny rozwój

THE INFLUENCE OF EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE JUNIOR'S DEVELOPMENT IN CONDITIONS OF THE NEW UKRAINIAN SCHOOL

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Abstract. The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, implementing the reform of secondary schools, provides for establishment of a school where children will be trained through activities, while focus will be on development of competencies but not memorizing facts. The article reveals the main goal of innovations – establishment of the New Ukrainian School, a center of knowledge and opportunities for self-realization and comprehensive personal development of each child. It has been determined that the elementary school is the basis (base) for the child's all further development (the child's comprehensive development in accordance with age and individual psychophysiological features and needs), its perception and attitude to learning. The reformation of the modern educational branch involves concern about educational environment is substantiated. It is determined that the main thing here is not machinery or furniture, but change of educational environment, which involves change of the child's attitude: respect, attention to it and a desire to find the best way for its effective training.

Key words: environment, educational environment, new Ukrainian school, harmonious development

ВПЛИВ ОСВІТНЬОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА НА РОЗВИТОК МОЛОДШОГО ШКОЛЯРА В УМОВАХ НОВОЇ УКРАЇНСЬКОЇ ШКОЛИ

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Анотація: Міністерство освіти і науки України, здійснюючи реформу середнього шкільництва, передбачає створення школи, де діти будуть навчатися через діяльність, а основна увага спрямована на розвиток компетентностей, а не запам'ятовування фактів. У статті розкрито головну мету нововведень – створення Нової української школи, осередку знань і можливостей для самореалізації та всебічного особистісного розвитку кожної дитини. Визначено, що початкова школа є основою (базою), на якій вибудовується весь подальший розвиток дитини (всебічний розвиток дитини відповідно до вікових та індивідуальних психофізіологічних особливостей і потреб), її сприйняття та ставлення до навчання. Обґрунтовано, що реформування сучасної освітньої галузі передбачає турботу про освітнє середовище. Визначено, що головним тут виступає не техніка чи меблі, а зміна освітнього середовища, яка передбачає зміну ставлення до дитини: повага, увага до неї і прагнення знайти оптимальний спосіб для її ефективного навчання.

Ключові слова: середовище, освітнє середовище, нова українська школа, гармонійний розвиток

Introduction.

At the current stage of society's development, education is being reformed. In order to provide high-quality educational services, the new Law of Ukraine "On Education" is being implemented in the state, implementation of measures envisaged by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine Decree No. 988-r of December 14, 2016 "On Approval of the Concept of Implementation of State Policy in the Field of General

Secondary Education Reform" New Ukrainian School for the Period till 2029 "and December 13, 2017 No. 903-p" On Approval of the Action Plan for 2017-2029 on the Implementation of the Concept for the Implementation of the State Policy in the Reform of General Secondary Education "But a Ukrainian school. "

As Oleksandr Savchenko notes, primary school, earlier than other levels of education, became the object of updating the educational process on the basis of childhood cynicism, partnership, taking into account the children's vital needs, developing new state standards, educational programs, evaluating educational results (Savchenko, 2018, p. 3).

It is in elementary school that the foundation of preparation for life is laid, intellectual, spiritual and physical formation of the personality is provided. In the elementary school children are interested in art, engaging in music and artistic and creative activities. The initial link of education is designed to form a holistic worldview and attitudes of students, to ensure the development of aesthetic ideals and tastes, a sense of responsibility for preserving the cultural heritage of society.

O. Savchenko notes that the goal of primary education is the comprehensive development of the child, his talents, abilities, competencies (key, general subjects, subject) and cross-cutting skills in accordance with age and individual psycho-physiological characteristics and needs, formation of values, development of autonomy, creativity and curiosity (Savchenko, 2018, p. 4). The child's comprehensive development involves mental, physical, and aesthetic. Common for all competencies are the so-called cross-cutting skills: reading with understanding, ability to express their own opinion orally and in writing, critical and system thinking, ability to logically justify a position, creativity, initiative, ability to constructively manage emotions, evaluate risks, make decisions, solve problems, ability to co-operate with other people.

We hope that in the New Ukrainian school all conditions will be created for the harmonious development of the younger generation. The Methodological Recommendations on the organization of the educational space of the New Ukrainian School state that the specialty of such a school is, among other things, the organization of such an educational environment that will promote the free development of the child's creative personality.

Main part. The purpose of our article is to theoretically substantiate the influence of the educational environment on the harmonious development of a junior high school student at the New Ukrainian School. Objectives of the study: to investigate the concept of "educational environment"; determine how the educational environment affects the development of a junior schoolboy; what conditions need to be created in the educational environment, so that the student can thoroughly develop and comfortably feel.

To achieve the purpose of the article and the solution of problems was used as a method of research, analysis of psychological and pedagogical, philosophical literature on the organization of the educational environment and its impact on the development of the individual.

The essence of the notion "educational environment" has been substantiated by both domestic and foreign psychologists and educators over the last decades. The study of the educational environment is carried out from the point of view of the modern understanding of education as a special sphere of social life, and the environment as a factor of education (N. Gontarovsky, S. Deryab, V. Zhelanova, V. Kozyrev, T. Meng, K.

Pridchochenko and etc.); generalized models of the educational environment (V. Davydov, Y. Korchak, V. Lebedev, V. Orlov, V. Panov, V. Rubtsov, V. Slobodchikov, V. Yasvin, etc.).

The term "educational environment" is interpreted by the researchers as: it is a collection of all possibilities of learning, upbringing and development of the individual, both positive and negative (Deryaba, 2007, p. 39); the system of influences and conditions for the formation of the individual according to the given model, as well as opportunities for its development, contained in the social and subject-spatial environment (Yasvin, 2001, p. 14); the product of relations between subjects of the educational space; a complex of additional factors that provide children with comfortable conditions for development, education and upbringing (Kruty, 2009, p. 35); the unity of social and substantive means of ensuring the diverse activities of the child (Novoselova, 1995, p. 21). The educational environment is developing if it is able to provide a set of opportunities for the self-development of all subjects in the educational process.

In particular, Sedova L. notes that the idea of creating a developing environment as a means of development and self-development of the child is not new for modern psychological and pedagogical science. Its formation is associated with the introduction in the Enlightenment of the term "environment", which was understood as certain social, material and spiritual conditions of human existence, its activities. It was found that the environment is one of the decisive factors in the formation and development of personality (Sedov, 1999, p. 27).

In psychological and pedagogical science there are several approaches to the definition of the concept of the educational environment as one of the most important factors in the development of personality. A number of researchers (B. Bim-Bad, A. Petrovsky, L. Sokhan, I. Ermakov, L. Novikov, Yu. Manuilov) believe that the educational environment is a sphere of vital activity of the child, which is constantly changing. It absorbs the wealth of pupils' interconnected culture with the surrounding world, teaches to remove knowledge from their own activities, from observation and perception, to reveal the vital importance of the objects being studied, to understand the principles of their actions and to guide them in new situations (that is, to carry out transfer, which occupies an important place in the educational process and practical life) (Bim-Bad, 1996, p. 6).

The educational environment in the psycho-pedagogical literature is also regarded as a subsystem of the socio-cultural environment as a combination of factors, circumstances, historical situations, and as the integrity of the specially organized conditions for the development of the student's personality (O. Gazman, E. Klimov, G. Kovalev, K. Levin, V. Panov, K. Rogers, V. Rubtsov, I. Slobodchikov, S. Tarasov, V. Yasvin, and others).

In particular, Y. Klimov distinguishes the following components of the educational environment: the social-contact component; information component; somatic component; substantive component. The social-contact component of the environment includes: a personal example of people around them, their culture, experience, lifestyle, behavior, relationships, etc., state institutions and organizations, groups of people and their representatives with whom the person interacts in one way or another; personal relationships in a group that is "native" to this person. The information component of the environment is created by certain rules that arise in the process of

personal interaction. The somatic part of the environment consists of a person's state of health, the state and capabilities of the human body. The substantive component includes material conditions of life, study, life, biological, hygienic conditions, microclimate, air purity, etc.) (*Klimov, 1969, p.*).

Unlike E. Klimova, G. Kovalev distinguishes the following structural components of the educational environment: the physical environment - the room, its design, the size and spatial structure of the study facilities, the conditions for the transfer and placement of students; - the human factor - the selection of students, the filling of classes and groups and its impact on the social behavior of students, the characteristics and success of students, ethnic characteristics, the quality of teacher training, gender-age structure of the student contingent; training program - the innovative nature of the contents of study programs, teaching technology, the style and methods of teaching, the forms of educational activity, the nature of control (*Gontarovskaya, 1996, p. 6*).

Most authors agree that the central among other structural components of the educational environment is the psychological component (social or communicative component in terms of different authors). The psychological component of the educational environment is, first of all, the nature of the communication of the subjects of the educational process. This component carries the main load on providing opportunities for satisfaction and development of the needs of the subjects of the educational process in the sense of security, in preserving and improving self-esteem, in the formation of a positive "I-concept, in recognition of the other, in a respectful attitude to himself and to around, in self-actualization. As a key psychological characteristic of the educational environment of the educational institution, many scholars (I. Baiva, S. Vershlovsky, O. Lebedev, V. Slobodchikov, etc.) consider the safety and psychologically safe educational environment as a condition for the positive personal growth of its participants.

V. Slobodchikov considers the educational environment as a specially organized space, a "place" in a society where subjectively there are many relations, relationships and various activities of various systems of individual development and socialization. The scientist believes that the specific property of the educational environment is its saturation of educational resources. The saturation of the environment with educational resources transforms it into an educational environment. In his view, the boundaries of the educational space can expand and narrow, they are determined by the scale of professional activity of teachers, the scale of involvement of the socio-cultural environment in the educational activity itself. This activity is reduced to the size of a separate institution, one program, one subject, transforms the space into a set of atomized places of education, destroying its unity and continuity (*Slobodchikov, 2000, p. 176*).

Y. Kulyutkin notes that "the educational environment can be characterized as a set of social, cultural, as well as specially organized in a educational institution psychological and pedagogical conditions, as a result of interaction with which the individual is becoming an individual" (*Kulyutkin, 2001, p. 6*).

Along with the term "educational environment", the notion "developing environment", "educational and development environment" is considered. As O. Pysarchuk notes, in the broadest context, the educational-developing environment is a socio-cultural space, within which a process of personality development is carried out with different degrees of organization. According to the author, in order for the

educational space to become a developing environment, it must acquire the following properties: flexibility; continuity; variability; Integration; openness; the mood for a joint active communication of all subjects of the educational process (*Pisarchuk, 2016, p.4*).

The organization of educational developmental environment is defined as: the provision of a set of conditions associated with material and technical and programmatic and methodological provision of the educational process; creation of conditions for creative comfortable interaction of children between themselves, with teachers, parents; using various methods and means of activating activity that provides creative development of personality.

Different aspects of the influence of the educational environment on the development of the child have been reflected in the modern scientific researches of I. Baeva, B. Bim-Bad, I. Bulakh, A. Valitskaya, V. Verbitsky, B. Wolfov, I. Ermakov, A. Katushova, E. Klimova, O. Kobernik, N. Kudikina, Yu. Manuilova, L. Novikova, A. Petrovsky, H. Pustovita, A. Sbrueva, V. Slobodchikova, L. Sokhan and others.

Consequently, the educational environment - a set of objective external conditions, factors, social objects, necessary for the successful functioning of education. It is a system of influences and conditions for the formation of the individual, as well as opportunities for its development, which are contained in the social and spatial-subject environment.

The importance of solving the problem of creating an educational environment today is conditioned by the need for its holistic renewal and alignment with the general transformational changes that take place in society. Changing the educational environment is a change in the attitude of the child: respect, attention to it and the desire to find the best way for its effective learning. This is exactly what the New Ukrainian School should be like. The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine approved the Methodological Recommendations on the organization of the educational space of the New Ukrainian School. In particular, the document states that the feature of the New Ukrainian School is, among other things, the organization of such an educational environment that will facilitate the free development of the child's creative personality. To this end, the spatial-subject environment, programs and means of training change.

Planning and designing the educational space of the school are aimed at developing the child and motivating her to study. General purpose equipment must meet the aesthetic requirements: to have an attractive appearance, modern design; compliance with the general style of the premises (https://osvita.ua/legislation/Ser_osv/60372/).

The school in which the student is during the school day begins with a nursery school. The appearance of the school, the decorating of the premises, study rooms, corridors, and the improvement of the preschool manor are of great importance for the comprehensive development of elementary school students. Multi-faceted and expedient use of school interior is possible only in case when its aesthetics will meet modern requirements. Modern aesthetic design of school interiors should promote the aesthetic education of children, develop their imagination, individual aesthetic tastes, and stimulate creative activity in various activities.

During the aesthetic design of the school interior, you can use such arts as monumental, decorative-applied and propaganda-registration.

According to N. Artemenko, "the aesthetics of school life is the situation of classes, offices, halls, corridors, etc. Lobby decoration, the design of a cool corner,

stands - all these are silent assistants of the teacher in the aesthetic, and, consequently, in the ethical the upbringing of schoolchildren, or his enemies "(Artemenko, 1978, p. 14).

Elementary school is a classroom with an established learning environment equipped with modern learning equipment and school equipment in accordance with sanitary and hygiene standards and regulations.

In accordance with the methodological recommendations of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine regarding the organization of the educational space of the New Ukrainian School, the educational environment should contribute to the free development of the child's creative personality. And this can be done through the creation of peculiar centers of pupils' activity in the classroom, in particular the educational-cognitive center of activity, thematic thematic centers, a cell for the game and artistic and creative activity, a corner of the wildlife, a recreation center, a children's library and a teacher's cell with the proper equipment.

The initial element of the school is the first to test new standards for Nursery and New Educational Space, where stands are an integral part of the design of elementary school cabinets. The introduction of new standards completely opens up new demands for student material delivery, new ideas for motivating students to learn, and radically change their design. Special attention is paid to the design, because the modern educational process requires changes not only in the process of information, but also in the design. Beautiful design directly affects the effectiveness of the educational process, where, with the help of various color schemes, drawings on the walls, posters, stands for the elementary school, creates an interesting, motivating, educational atmosphere, which is so lacking today.

According to the Regulation on the study rooms of general educational establishments, approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated July 20, 2004, No. 601 (<https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z1121-04>), a school room for students elementary classes should be aesthetically appealing. In educational rooms for junior pupils, color monotony should be avoided. You need to create a cheerful atmosphere.

For registration of the Cabinet it is foreseen the creation of educational and methodical expositions of variable and permanent character. The permanent expositions of the cabinet of primary classes include: state symbols; rules of fire safety and traffic; a cool place where the rights and responsibilities of schoolchildren, rules of student behavior, self-government, and the life of the class collective are reflected.

In section cabinets of the cabinet are shown devices, collections of photo exhibitions, etc. Expositions of variable character include: exhibition of the best works of students; materials for the topic of the following lessons, indicative tasks of the thematic evaluation, state certification; additional information according to the curriculum; results of experimental and research work of students; results of student competitions, tournaments, etc.

The idea behind the design of school rooms in elementary school is that the walls of the school, its interior attract children's attention to such important aspects of our lives as ergonomics and aesthetics. Therefore, the school should not have standard classes, corridors and a boring lobby. But there should be a lot of bright and fun elements, and modern design solutions should be applied (*Bespala*, http://freepapers.ru/16/shlyahi-ta-zasobi-estetichnogo_vihovannya/ / 292273.2002739.list1.html).

It is important in the elementary school to decorate the premises, but it should not be placed on the front wall, because it diverts the attention of students from the board. The main thing in color design of school premises is the maximum comfort of its students. First of all it concerns the elementary school, where the first learning skills and social behavior are formed. A schoolboy should feel comfortable at school everywhere - in the school room, gym, recreation room, library, dining room, in the school yard, even looking at the premises of the school and the adjoining territory. Under such conditions, the state of health improves, the interest of children in the process of learning increases, the ability to fully absorb learning material increases significantly.

The criteria of evaluation of the functioning of the educational environment are determined: the educational environment provides for the harmonious development of children; the effectiveness of children's creative and research activity; creation of conditions for self-realization of personality in creative activity; the ability of the environment to meet the needs of the child and to form a system of social and spiritual values in it. An integrated criterion for the quality of the educational environment is its ability to provide all subjects of the educational process a system of opportunities for effective personal self-development.

Conclusions.

Thus, having made the theoretical substantiation of the problem under study we can conclude that the functional possibilities of the educational environment consist of the following components: various types of active, conscious and useful activity of students: educational, professional, sports, labor, creative, cognitive, social, economic, ecological, aesthetic and others. Life situations, discussions, and conversations in informal settings are also important; great saturation of sensory stimuli: design of the premises, aesthetics of the natural and social environment, works of art and architecture; spatial and temporal mobility in the organization of diverse student activities. The school should have a favorable psychological climate, a positive emotional and psychological atmosphere in the students' and pedagogical groups.

In the future, we plan to experiment with the study of the influence of the educational environment on the harmonious development of a junior schoolboy.

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